

Templates and Datasets for Replication Package

1. SQA Scenario Template

Element	Description
Source	
Stimulus	
Artifact	
Environment	
Response	
Response Measure	

2. SIG Template (Structure)

Root Softgoal (QA_ASR) |-- ZT Principle Softgoal (P1/P2/P3) |-- Operational Softgoal |-- Security Mechanism Repeat refinement until mechanisms can be directly mapped to scenarios.

3. Sample ZT Mechanisms Dataset

ID	Mechanism	ZT Principle
A11	Continuous Authentication	Verify Explicitly
A16	Attribute-Based Access Control	Verify Explicitly / Least Privilege
A8	Micro-segmentation	Assume Breach
A6	TLS Encrypted Communication	Assume Breach

4. Evaluation Questionnaire Template

- The method is easy to understand.
- The method is easy to apply in practice.
- The method helps identify ZT-related design concerns.
- The method improves traceability between ASRs, QAs, and scenarios.
- The softgoal trees help understand how ZT principles influence quality attributes.